

A Series Representation of Analytically Continuous Complex Functions with Negative Powers

Devin Hardy

Abstract: First a proof of Taylor's Theorem is established by Integration by Parts, and then generalization of the IBP formula to \mathbb{C} is used to derive Taylor's Theorem for Complex numbers z . A similar method to that which is used to derive Taylor's Theorem is used to derive a Complex valued series representation similar to the Taylor Series but for negative powers.

In general to obtain a Taylor polynomial [0] for a function, apply the operation that is the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus (FTOC) [1] to the definition of some continuously differentiable function f [2], then apply the operation of Integration By Parts (IBP) [3] infinitely many times to the formula obtained from the operation of FOTC to obtain the Taylor Expansion Equation [4]. This is best and most appropriately proven by first recalling the fundamentals of Calculus:

Definition #1:

$\lim_{x \rightarrow t} f(x) = L$ means that for each given $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a corresponding $\delta > 0$ such that $|f(x) - L| < \epsilon$ whenever $0 < |x - t| < \delta$.

Definition #2:

$\lim_{x \rightarrow t^+} f(x) = L$ means that for each given $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a corresponding $\delta > 0$ such that $|f(x) - L| < \epsilon$ whenever $0 < (x - t) < \delta$.

Definition #3:

$\lim_{x \rightarrow t^-} f(x) = L$ means that for each given $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a corresponding $\delta > 0$ such that $|f(x) - L| < \epsilon$ whenever $0 < (t - x) < \delta$.

Begin with the definition of the derivative:

$$\frac{df(x)}{dx} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(f(x + \Delta x) - f(x))}{\Delta x} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left(f\left(x + \frac{(b-a)}{n}\right) - f(x) \right)}{\frac{(b-a)}{n}} \tag{Eq 0}$$

$\Delta x = \frac{(b-a)}{n}$, gives the equality of limits [8] to change the variables $\Delta x \rightarrow \Delta x(n)$ from the middle equation to the equation on the right hand side (RHS). In other words, the limit definition which is used whether it is chosen to select $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty}$ instead of $\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0}$, changes how the limit must be evaluated. This is because in this case n is proportional to the reciprocal of Δx and where one definition means zero, that exact point is infinity relative to n .

There are many derivative rules such as Power Laws, derivatives of Hyperbolic functions, derivatives of integrals, derivatives of exponential and logarithmic functions, and derivatives of trigonometric functions to name a few but what is important for what this paper is concerned with is the product rule and to save time in this paper it is only proven for some of the relevant rules as is the case for the other integration rules as well as the limit rules and other fundamentals of calculus which clearly belong to a much larger subject than that of this short paper which mostly only concerned with generalizing the Taylor Expansion and not all the other interesting things in Calculus. We can prove the product rule with the definition of the derivative above and defining the analytically continuous function $H(x) = (f(x)g(x))$, and inserting this into **Eq 0**, so that we have:

$$\frac{dH(x)}{dx} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(H(x + \Delta x) - H(x))}{\Delta x} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(f(x + \Delta x)g(x + \Delta x) - f(x)g(x))}{\Delta x} \tag{Eq 1}$$

By adding and subtracting zero in the numerator of **Eq 1**) the form of $f(x + \Delta x)g(x)$, we can write the RHS as:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(f(x)g(x)) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(f(x + \Delta x)g(x + \Delta x) - f(x + \Delta x)g(x) + f(x + \Delta x)g(x) - f(x)g(x))}{\Delta x} \quad \text{Eq 2)}$$

Regrouping terms of **Eq 2** by grouping the like terms and using the property of adding fractions with the same denominator produces:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(f(x)g(x)) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{f(x + \Delta x)(g(x + \Delta x) - f(x + \Delta x)g(x))}{\Delta x} \right) + \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{g(x)(f(x + \Delta x) - f(x)g(x))}{\Delta x} \right) \quad \text{Eq 3)}$$

Pulling the $g(x)$ out of the like terms in the numerator of **Eq 3** on the RHS of the RHS of **Eq 3** and $f(x + \Delta x)$ on the LHS of the RHS of **Eq 3** gives:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(f(x)g(x)) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \left(f(x + \Delta x) \left(\frac{(g(x + \Delta x) - g(x))}{\Delta x} \right) \right) + \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \left(g(x) \left(\frac{(f(x + \Delta x) - f(x))}{\Delta x} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 4)}$$

Whereupon, insertion of $\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} f(x + \Delta x) = f(x)$ and utilization of the product limit properties and the independence of Δx , **Eq 4** can be written as:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(f(x)g(x)) = \left(f(x) \left(\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(g(x + \Delta x) - g(x))}{\Delta x} \right) \right) + \left(g(x) \left(\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(f(x + \Delta x) - f(x))}{\Delta x} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 5)}$$

With the definition of the derivative, **Eq 0** for g and f in **Eq 5** being inserted, the product rule for the derivative can be derived:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(f(x)g(x)) = f(x) \left(\frac{dg(x)}{dx} \right) + g(x) \left(\frac{df(x)}{dx} \right) \quad \text{Eq 6)}$$

But what happens with the application of the k th derivative to a product? By repeated application of the derivative rule an equation for the k th derivative can be obtained and this has been done before and expanding this is easily done but tedious and takes a lot of page space so instead of reinventing the wheel gratuitously, the General Leibniz Rule [6] is:

$$\frac{d^k}{dx^k}(f(x)g(x)) = \sum_{n=0}^k \binom{k}{n} f^{k-n} g^n \quad \text{Eq 7)}$$

From combinatorics the binomial coefficient provides the number of possible ways to choose a subset of objects from a larger set of objects and these are coefficients within the binomial theorem. The formula for the binomial coefficients is:

$$\binom{k}{n} = \frac{k!}{n!(k-n)!} \quad \text{Eq 8)}$$

In other words, for the k th application, or the k th operation of the derivative on a product fg this produces a formula that is a sum of the $(k-n)$ th derivatives of f and the n th derivatives of g with binomial coefficients. The second part of the FTC relating the definite integral to Riemann Sums as shown below:

$$A(x) = \text{Area Under the Curve of } f(x) = \int_a^b f(x) dx = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i) \Delta x \quad \text{Eq 9)}$$

The interval $x \in [a, b]$ is divided into n increments of the size $\Delta x = \frac{(b-a)}{n}$ with boundaries of the rectangles at (x_k, x_{k+1}) for k rectangles where $x_k = a + k\Delta x$. The definition of the unit infinitesimal $dx = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \Delta x = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(b-a)}{n}$.

The first part of fundamental Theorem of Calculus for 1 variable can be stated as:

$$f(x) = f(a) + \int_a^x \frac{df(t)}{dt} dt \quad \text{Eq 10)}$$

Or in other words, the integral is the antiderivative of f . Taking the antiderivative of both sides of **Eq 6** gives:

$$(f(x)g(x)) = \int f(t) \left(\frac{dg(t)}{dt} \right) dt + \int g(t) \left(\frac{df(t)}{dt} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 11)}$$

Now subtract $\int g(x) \left(\frac{df(x)}{dx} \right)$ from both sides of **Eq 11** to obtain The integration by parts formula:

$$\int_a^x f(t) \left(\frac{dg(t)}{dt} \right) dt = f(t)g(t)|_a^x - \int_a^x g(t) \left(\frac{df(t)}{dt} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 12)}$$

The second FTOC is:

$$H(x) - H(a) = \int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 13)}$$

By using the IBP formula, **Eq 12**, and inserting $\frac{dg(t)}{dt} = 1$, and the antiderivative is $g(t) = (t + c)$ and $f(t) = \frac{dH}{dt}$ into **Eq 13** produces:

$$\int_a^x \frac{dH}{dt} (1) dt = \frac{dH(t)}{dt} (t + c)|_a^x - \int_a^x (t + c) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 14)}$$

With direct insertion of **Eq 14** into the integral in **Eq 13** produces the expression:

$$H(x) - H(a) = \frac{dH(t)}{dt} (t + c)|_a^x - \int_a^x (t + c) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 15)}$$

If x is a constant relative to t then it is possible that $c = c(x)$ because $\frac{\partial c(x)}{\partial t} = 0$ since the integration is relative to t . Any such constant which is independent of t can be selected such as $c = -x$. There might be n such constants of integration with $c(x) = c_n(x)$ with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} c_n$ but for each of these setting $c_n = -x$ can be done since $\frac{\partial c_n}{\partial t} = 0$. And this can be done as well using $\frac{dg(t)}{dt} = (t - x)$ and defining the antiderivative $g = \frac{(t-x)^2}{2}$ and $f(t) = \frac{d^2F(t)}{dt^2}$

$$\int_a^x (t - x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt = \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t - x)^2}{2} |_a^x - \int_a^x \frac{(t - x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 16)}$$

Now **Eq 15** has a polynomial expression to the degree three with an error term given by an integral. Inserting **Eq 16** into the integral on the RHS of **Eq 15** produces:

$$H(x) - H(a) = \frac{dH(t)}{dt} (t - x)|_a^x - \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t - x)^2}{2} |_a^x + \int_a^x \frac{(t - x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 17)}$$

The error term is defined by the remainder function: $R_3(x) = \int_a^x \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt$

Applying IBP to the integral in **Eq 17** gives:

$$\int_a^x \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t - x)^2}{2!} \right) dt = \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t - x)^3}{3!} \right) |_a^x - \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t - x)^3}{3!} \right) \left(\frac{d^4H(t)}{dt^4} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 18)}$$

Now inserting **Eq 18** into the integral in **Eq 17** transforms **Eq 13** to:

Eq 19)

$$H(x) - H(a) = \frac{dH(t)}{dt}(t-x)|_a^x - \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} |_a^x - \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) |_a^x - \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) \left(\frac{d^4H(t)}{dt^4} \right) dt$$

Eq 19) is the 3rd degree remainder term plus the 3rd degree polynomial term for the series approximation to the Taylor series.

Operation Number	Remainder Term	IBP formulae	Approximate Taylor Formulae
\widehat{IBP}_1	$R_0(x) = \int_{t=a}^{t=x} (-1)^1 \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt$	$\int_a^x \frac{dH}{dt}(1) dt$ $= \frac{dH(t)}{dt}(t-x) _a^x$ $- \int_a^x (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt$	$\frac{H(x) - H(a)}{dt}(t-x) _a^x$ $- \int_a^x (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt$
\widehat{IBP}_2	$R_1(x) = \int_a^x (-1)^2 (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt$	$\int_a^x (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt$ $= \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} _a^x$ $- \int_a^x \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt$	$\frac{H(x) - H(a)}{dt}(t-x) _a^x$ $- \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} _a^x$ $+ \int_a^x \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt$
\widehat{IBP}_3	$R_2(x) = \int_a^x (-1)^3 \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt$	$\int_a^x \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t-x)^2}{2!} \right) dt$ $= \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) _a^x$ $- \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) \left(\frac{d^4H(t)}{dt^4} \right) dt$	$\frac{H(x) - H(a)}{dt}(t-x) _a^x$ $- \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} _a^x$ $+ \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) _a^x$ $- \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) \left(\frac{d^4H(t)}{dt^4} \right) dt$
\widehat{IBP}_k	$R_k(x) = \int_a^x (-1)^k \left(\frac{(t-x)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} \right) \left(\frac{d^kH(t)}{dt^k} \right) dt$	$\int_a^x \frac{d^kH(t)}{dt^k} \left(\frac{(t-x)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} \right) dt$ $= \frac{d^kH(t)}{dt^k} \left(\frac{(t-x)^k}{k!} \right) _a^x$ $- \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^k}{k!} \right) \left(\frac{d^{k+1}H(t)}{dt^{k+1}} \right) dt$	$\frac{H(x) - H(a)}{dt}(t-x) _a^x$ $- \sum_{n=0}^{n=k} (-1)^n \frac{d^nH(t)}{dt^n} \left(\frac{(t-x)^n}{n!} \right) _a^x$ $+ R_k(x)$

By defining the operator: \widehat{IBP}_n = nth application of IBP algorithm [7] This is defined in such a manner that:

$$\widehat{IBP}_1 \left(\int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt \right) = \frac{dH(t)}{dt}(t-x)|_a^x - \int_a^x (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{IBP}_2 \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt}(t-x)|_a^x - \int_a^x (t-x) \left(\frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \right) dt \right) \\ = \frac{dH(t)}{dt}(t-x)|_a^x - \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} |_a^x + \int_a^x \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 21)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \widehat{IBP}_3 \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} (t-x) \Big|_a^x - \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \Big|_a^x - \int_a^x \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \left(\frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \right) dt \right) \\
&= \frac{dH(t)}{dt} (t-x) \Big|_a^x - \frac{d^2H(t)}{dt^2} \frac{(t-x)^2}{2} \Big|_a^x + \frac{d^3H(t)}{dt^3} \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) \Big|_a^x \\
&\quad - \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^3}{3!} \right) \left(\frac{d^4H(t)}{dt^4} \right) dt
\end{aligned} \tag{Eq 22}$$

Application of IBP k times to **Eq 13**) can be written as: \widehat{IBP}_k (**Eq 13**) and following the pattern from **Eq 20** – **Eq 22**), \widehat{IBP}_k (**Eq 13**) can be written as:

$$\prod_{k=1}^n \widehat{IBP}_k \left(\int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt \right) = \sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left(\frac{(t-x)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^kH}{dt^k} \right) \right) \Big|_{t=a}^{t=x} + R_n(x) \tag{Eq 23}$$

Where

$$R_n(x) = \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^n}{n!} \right) \left(\frac{d^{n+1}H(t)}{dt^{n+1}} \right) dt \tag{Eq 24}$$

Where **Eq 24**) is the integral definition of the n th order remainder term. It is fair to say that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty}$ **Eq 23**) derives the Taylor Theorem. So, taking the limit:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \widehat{IBP}_k \left(\int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt \right) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left(\frac{(t-x)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^kH}{dt^k} \right) \right) \Big|_{t=a}^{t=x} \right) + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(t-x)^n}{n!} \right) \left(\frac{d^{n+1}H(t)}{dt^{n+1}} \right) dt
\end{aligned} \tag{Eq 25}$$

There is an oscillation for the remainder terms but the negative signs multiply into the odd terms to produce the regular positive Taylor coefficients and the even terms negativity essentially cancels from the squaring which results in the positivity of the end expression in the usual form of the Taylor Series. The oscillation is perfectly balanced by this property, the fact that \forall even powers of negative one k , $(-1)^k = 1$. Then the binomial part can be written as $(t-x)^k (-1)^k$ where when k is even, $(t-x)^{k_{even}} (-1)^{k_{even}} = (1)(x-t)^{k_{even}}$. Even powers, can be written as $k_{even} = 2k$ for a positive integer k . This suggests that: $(t-x)^{k_{even}} (-1)^{k_{even}} = (1)((-1)(x-t))^{2k} = ((-1)(x-t))^{k^2}$ for which it can be stated that a positive number because $(-1)^{k_{odd}^2} = (-1)^2 = 1$ this is proof as to why the negative sign disappears for the even powers. For odd powers the negative sign does not go away however because there is the action of subtracting from the evaluation between bounds of integration so this negative sign cancels the other negative sign with the conversion $(t-x) = (-1)(x-t)$ and the subtraction essentially makes this negative sign go away for the odd terms. The extra negative term for the even powered terms essentially is why the even terms are positive as well.

The remainder is getting smaller and smaller since most of the information is stored in the first n terms of the Taylor series where $R_n(x) < R_{n-1}(x) < R_{n-2}(x) \dots R_0(x)$, and the denominator grows in proportion to $n!$. With the recursive expression of the terms as $a_n = \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} \approx \frac{x^n}{n!}$ and $a_{n+1} = \frac{x^{n+1}}{(n+1)!}$. Using the ratio test, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{x}{n+1} \rightarrow 0$ so it must be true that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} R_n(x) = 0$. In other words the remainder term at infinity converges to zero. To be more precise the convergence of R_n to 0 could alternately be proven with the mean value theorem for integrals.

Explicitly writing the LHS of **Eq 25**):

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \widehat{IBP}_k \left(\int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{dH(t)}{dt} \right) dt \right) \quad \text{Eq 26)}$$

By definition, **Eq 26)** is the RHS of **Eq 13)**, so inserting **Eq 26)** into the RHS of **Eq 13)** gives the expression:

$$H(x) - H(a) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \widehat{IBP}_k \left(\int_{t=a}^{t=x} \left(\frac{H(t)}{dt} \right) dt \right) \quad \text{Eq 27)}$$

Which allows us to arrive to Taylors theorem by **Eq 25)** and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} R_n(x) = 0$ is inserted into **Eq 27)**:

$$H(x) - H(a) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left(\frac{(t-x)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k H}{dt^k} \right) \right) \Big|_{t=a}^{t=x} \right) \quad \text{Eq 28)}$$

Moving $H(a)$ over to the RHS produces the standard form of Taylors Theorem:

$$H(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k H}{dt^k} \right) \Big|_a \right) \quad \text{Eq 29)}$$

The Maclaurin series formula can be derived from here simply with $a = 0$. The key difference between each polynomial is the coefficients which are essentially given by the derivative at a , the value a we are expanding around, and the factorial k . The factorial k however appears with all functions and is not unique to any function. The only thing unique to each function is the set of derivatives for which the space is continuous on the function.

The formula for the n th application of the IBP can be written as:

$$\widehat{IBP}_k \left(\int_a^x f \left(\frac{d^n g}{dt^n} \right) dt \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^k \left(\frac{d^k g}{dt^k} \right) \left(\frac{d^{n-1-k} f}{dt^{n-1-k}} \right) + (-1)^n \int_a^x \frac{d^n f}{dt^n} g dt \quad \text{Eq 30)}$$

The Taylor series can be generalized with the general Leibniz rule if we define some function $H(x) = f(x)g(x)$, and its Taylor series can be written by insertion of **Eq 7)** into **Eq 29)**:

$$H(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k H(a)}{dx^k} \right) \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\sum_{n=0}^k \binom{k}{n} f^{k-n} g^n(a) \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 31)}$$

The n th application of the chain rule gives us a way to look at coordinate transformations. How does the Taylor formula transform with a coordinate transform $x \rightarrow x'$? By the chain rule, $\frac{d}{dx} = \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}$, and for the second derivative:

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) = \frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \quad \text{Eq 32)}$$

Now taking the third derivative

$$\frac{d^3}{dx^3} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \right) = \frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2}$$

And rearranging

$$\frac{d^3}{dx^3} = \frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + 2 \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3}$$

Gives

$$\frac{d^3}{dx^3} = \frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} \quad \text{Eq 33)}$$

The fourth order derivative is:

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) \right) + 3 \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} = \frac{d^4 x'}{dx^4} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \frac{d}{dx} \left(3 \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \right) + \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^4}{dx^4} &= \frac{d^4 x'}{dx^4} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) \\ &+ \left(3 \left(\left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} \right) \\ &+ \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x'^4} \end{aligned}$$

Which can be written as

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} = \frac{d^4 x'}{dx^4} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} + 3 \left(\left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \right) \right) \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x'^4} \quad \text{Eq 34)}$$

We may write the nth operation of the derivative as:

$$\prod_{k=1}^n \widehat{D}_k \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) = \frac{d^n}{dx^n} = \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^n \quad \text{Eq 35)}$$

And also since it is implied that the operator is multiplied into itself n times **Eq 35)** can be written in the form:

$$\widehat{D}_n = \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^n \quad \text{Eq 36)}$$

Summarizing derivative operations:

Operator Number	Derivative unprimed	Primed Derivative relative to x
\widehat{D}_1	$\frac{d}{dx}$	$\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}$
\widehat{D}_2	$\frac{d^2}{dx^2}$	$\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2}$
\widehat{D}_3	$\frac{d^3}{dx^3}$	$\frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3}$

\widehat{D}_4	$\frac{d^4}{dx^4}$	$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d^4 x'}{dx^4} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) \\ & + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \\ & + 3 \left(\left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d^3 x'}{dx^3} \right) \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \\ & + \left(\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2} \right) \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x'^3} + \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x'^4} \end{aligned}$
-----------------	--------------------	--

It is not clear what the formula for the k th derivative might be. Proceeding, the operator notation allows the integral to be defined using Leibnitz notation as the negative values of the derivative operator in **Eq 36**) such that:

$$\hat{I}_k = \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^{-k} = \left(\int dx \right)^k \quad \text{Eq 37)}$$

This goes to say that $\widehat{D}_k = \hat{I}_{-k}$, $\widehat{D}_{-k} = \hat{I}_k$. It seems kind of gratuitous to express the derivative as an operator in Quantum Mechanics [8] as well as Operator Theory [9] have shown the power of expressing the derivative as an Operator as well as the Integral. Expressing it this way however makes it very clear exactly what is producing the large equations in a compact sense because otherwise we would have to explicitly write k first derivatives multiplied together. As well as quantum mechanics refer to operator theory for a fuller discussion on the mathematical legality of this expression.

Here with operator notation, the n th application of the chain rule for derivatives on some function H can be obtained if $H = H(f(g(x)))$. It turns out that there indeed an exact formula for the n th application of the chain rule, and that is given by the Faa' di Bruno's formula [10]:

$$\frac{d^k f(g(x))}{dx^k} = \sum \frac{n!}{m_1! m_2! \dots m_k!} \cdot f^{(\Sigma m_k)}(g(x)) \cdot \prod_{j=1}^k \left(\frac{g^j(x)}{j!} \right)^{m_j} \quad \text{Eq 38)}$$

Defining the k th derivative as an operator and using the substitution above we obtain: $\frac{d}{dx} = \frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'}$. The existence of $\frac{d^2 x'}{dx^2}$ from our nonlinear transformation implies that the transformation from

$$\frac{d^k f(g(x))}{dx^k} \quad \text{Eq 39)}$$

The primed frame can be determined with the chain rule formula above if only we replace with x in $g(x)$, x' . Then we have

$$\frac{d^k f(g(x))}{dx^k} = \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^k f(g(x')) \quad \text{Eq 40)}$$

The operator is in the k th degree, essentially is in this representation taking the derivative k times, or applying the derivative operation k times, or multiplying on the left hand side of the function the single derivative k times. This gives the ability for us to convert with our representation above. The partial derivative equations on the last part of the last page using the definition of the operator shows what the equations will expand to. The equation becomes:

$$\frac{d^k f(g(x))}{dx^k} = \left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^k f(g(x')) \quad \text{Eq 41)}$$

Now we take the Taylor expansion

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k f(a)}{dx^k} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 42)}$$

and directly insert **Eq 41** into **Eq 42** to obtain:

$$f(x') = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x'-a')^k}{k!} \left(\left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^k f(x') \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 43)}$$

Which with operator notation allows **Eq 43** to be written as:

$$f(x') = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x'-a')^k}{k!} \left(\widehat{D}_k f(x') \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 44)}$$

Now, generalizing these two equations further to include the general Taylor expansion for the chain rule, replace the definitions of the functions with some other function not yet used. Then define $H(x) = f(g(x))$. If the derivative of H exists, then the function is analytic and has a Taylor series of the form **Eq 29) = Eq 45)**:

$$H(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k H(a)}{dx^k} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 45)}$$

Then a transformation of coordinates transforms **Eq 45** to:

$$H(x') = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x'-a')^k}{k!} \left(\left(\frac{dx'}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^k H(x') \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 46)}$$

Eq 46) can be written with the derivative operator notation in Eq 36) such as:

$$H(x') = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x'-a')^k}{k!} \left(\widehat{D}_k H(x') \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 47)}$$

Using the chain rule formula **Eq 38)**, and inserting this into **Eq 45)**, this produces:

$$H(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x-a)^k}{k!} \left(\sum_{m_1! m_2! \dots m_k!} \frac{n!}{m_1! m_2! \dots m_k!} \cdot f^{(\sum m_k)}(g(a)) \cdot \prod_{j=1}^k \left(\frac{g^j(a)}{j!} \right)^{m_j} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 49)}$$

Certainly the primed Taylor expansion exists symmetrically with $H'(x') = \widehat{D}_k H(x') = f'(g'(x))$ in which case, the Taylor Expansion can be represented in the symmetric form to the primed function by priming each value in **Eq 49)**:

$$H(x') = \sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} \left(\frac{(x'-a')^k}{k!} \left(\sum_{m_1! m_2! \dots m_k!} \frac{n!}{m_1! m_2! \dots m_k!} \cdot f'^{(\sum m_k)}(g'(a)) \cdot \prod_{j=1}^k \left(\frac{g'^j(a')}{j!} \right)^{m_j} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 50)}$$

The primed here is not to be confused with the first derivative where the prime means first derivative. It seemingly is best to explicitly define first and second order derivatives and use the power notation for the derivatives for the general formula for H to avoid this confusion. Using the same approach the $H(x)$ function can be derived for the product $f(x)g(x)$ as well as and other form of functions which have mathematical operations on them that define a general function $H(x)$ such as a function which needs the n th chain rule and n th product rule application for the Complex derivative.

Using the n th order chain rule formula **Eq 49)**, the nonlinear relationship between the x and x' coordinate transform of the Taylor polynomial can be established as in **Eq 50)**. The Taylor polynomial since, the k th derivative is a sum itself can be written as a nested sum, giving an expression for the primed coordinate polynomial. Essentially

this comes from inserting primed coordinates into the standard proof of the Taylors theorem and evaluating these coordinates for various functions and values, including complex.

Further generalization essentially comes down to considering that $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are Complex valued Tensors [11] as well as having n Real coordinates. Then the definitions of f and g can be varied [12] so long as they follow the appropriately modified fundamental theorem of calculus for the definitions of those mathematical objects and the derivatives are continuous.

DIFFERENTIABILITY OF COMPLEX VALUED FUNCTIONS

A Complex function is Holomorphic [13] if its Complex derivative [14] in a neighborhood of each point in a domain in the complex plane. Defining the Complex derivative can be done analogously to the 1 variable derivative formula **Eq 0**) as long as appropriate generalizations are made for the definition of the variable with use of a parameterized variable t :

$$\frac{df}{dz} = \lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{f(z + \Delta z) - f(z)}{\Delta z} \right) \quad \text{Eq 51)}$$

Using this form of the derivative all the known rules of the complex derivative and see their relationships to the Real analytic case can be produced. An alternate path to define the derivative is with the Wirtinger derivatives and Wirtinger operators [15]: The Wirtinger derivatives are defined as the following linear partial differential operators of first order [16]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 52)}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z'} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & +\frac{i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 53)}$$

Unconventionally this paper is using primed coordinates for the purpose of generalization but with the selection of conjugate symmetry $z' = \bar{z}$: These transformation equations **Eq 52)** and **Eq 53)** can be expressed with the matrix notation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{i}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 54)}$$

These derivatives can be generalized to n dimensional complex numbers: $f(x_\mu) = U(x_\mu) + iV(x_\mu)$ for $\mu > 2$. Evidently when the Wirtinger derivative of f equals zero, the Riemann Cauchy conditions can be derived. In this notation applying the operator **Eq 54)** to $f(z)$ and setting this quantity equal to zero gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \end{pmatrix} f(z) = 0 &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{i}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{i}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} f(z) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \\ \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + i \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial z'} + i \frac{\partial v}{\partial z'} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 55)}$$

With this primed representation it permits the definition of x' and y' operators and partial derivatives. This essentially suggests that the function:

$$D(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} UD(x, y) + iVD(x, y) \\ UD'(x, y) + iVD'(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \end{pmatrix} f(z) \quad \text{Eq 56)}$$

Is extremized when the Riemann-Cauchy conditions are satisfied. An interesting relation happens when with the definition for the $D(x, y)$ function with phasor-2vector notation and the equality of nested matrices and in this case nested vectors, the matrix transform of the coordinate system by the derivative can be derived:

$$D(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) & \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \\ \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) & \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ i \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 57)}$$

Here, this shows the existence of $D(x, y)$ for a function can be expressed as a Real valued matrix. Then so long as we repeat this algorithm to define the derivative of the function, we can define $D^k(x, y)$ and insert this into the formula for the Taylors Theorem for complex numbers but we also have to more rigidly handle the integration so to ensure that when we apply IBP on the product of the complex functions $f(z)g(z)$, the formula is valid. But by expressing $D^k(x, y)$, it can be defined in the Taylor Expansion with the Multivariate Taylor Expansion Formula. The formula for the nth Wirtinger derivative is not clearly stated in literature and it was not obvious how to express the nth Wirtinger derivative. It would simplify the notation but for the point of this exercise the exact formula is not needed. Due to the fact that we may express the derivative of the function with the derivative for the multivariable chain rule:

$$\frac{df(x_\mu)}{dt} = \sum_{\mu=0}^{\mu=n} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_\mu} \left(\frac{dx_\mu}{dt} \right) \quad \text{Eq 58)}$$

Letting $\mu = 2$, and $\frac{dy}{dy} = i$ and $\frac{dx}{dt} = 1$, it can be seen that the Wirtinger or Complex derivative can be expressed by utilization of **Eq 58**). And setting the differential $df(x_\mu) = 0$ the Cauchy Riemann equations are given if $f(x_\mu) = U(x_\mu) + iV(x_\mu)$. In other words the Complex parameterization of the variable t converts the general derivative operator defined relative to t into the Complex derivative:

$$\left(\frac{d}{dz} \right) = \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \Big|_{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}=1, \frac{dy}{dt}=i \right)} \quad \text{Eq 59)}$$

From using the parameterization in **Eq 59**) and the definition of the derivative produced by complex parameterization described in **Eq 59**) in replacement of the variables in **Eq 58**) the Complex Taylor formula can be written as:

$$f(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k f}{dt^k} \right) \Big|_{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}=1, \frac{dy}{dt}=i \right)} \quad \text{Eq 60)}$$

Thus with parameterization of **Eq 58**) for the chain rule definition of the multivariate derivative we can directly state the rules that $U(x, y)$ and $iV(x, y)$ must follow as well as the being able to quickly derive the Taylor Expansion. The real analytic functions U and V must possess multivariate continuity and multivariate differentiability. Or in other words,

$$\frac{dU(x, y)}{dt} = \sum_{\mu=1}^{\mu=2} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_\mu} \left(\frac{dx_\mu}{dt} \right) \Big|_{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}=1, \frac{dy}{dt}=i \right)} \quad \text{Eq 61)}$$

$$\frac{dV(x, y)}{dt} = \sum_{\mu=1}^{\mu=2} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x_\mu} \left(\frac{dx_\mu}{dt} \right) \Big|_{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}=1, \frac{dy}{dt}=i \right)} \quad \text{Eq 62)}$$

Where in this case there is a parameterization of the variable t for real values, letting $\frac{dx}{dt} = 1$ and $\frac{dy}{dt} = i$ which essentially converts t into the complex number z .

The statement here that $\frac{dU(x,y)}{dt}$ is smooth and continuous implies that the partial derivatives of U and V are continuous. It should be stated that in order for f to exist as a Complex function the Riemann-Cauchy equations must be obeyed or in other words that the Complex derivative in the form above with the parameterizations must exist, but that furthermore, in order for f to be Complex differentiable, the standard 2 dimensional multivariable Calculus theorems must apply to U and V , and the matrix entries for $D(x, y)$. Proving this is easy since this must be true if the partial derivatives of U and V for x and y exist. The sum or difference of a continuous function is a continuous function and since $\frac{dU}{dt}$ and $\frac{dV}{dt}$ exist for all Real parameterizations, summation is performed over partial derivatives being applied to each of the functions. The statement that summarizes the representation is 2d fundamental Theorem of Calculus:

$$U(t_2) - U(t_1) = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dU}{dt} dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 63)}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} U(t_2) - U(t_1) \\ V(t_2) - V(t_1) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dU}{dt} dt \\ \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dV}{dt} dt \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 64)}$$

This parameterization suggests that setting $y = ix$, so that $s = x + iy$, a one dimensional Complex number. With this parameterization the Wirtinger derivatives take the form which was used to derive the Riemann-Cauchy conditions in **Eq 61)** and **Eq 62)**. The integrals over the variable t in **Eq 63)** and **Eq 64)** become contour integrals with the parameterization introduced in **Eq 59)**.

INTEGRATION OF COMPLEX VALUED FUNCTIONS

Theorem:

Using a coordinate transformation: $T(x, iy) \rightarrow (x', y')$ for some transform T , then

$$\begin{aligned} x' &\rightarrow x'(x, iy), \\ y' &\rightarrow y'(x, iy), \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 65)}$$

This implies that the contour in the complex plane is equivalent to some double integral of the integrand of the contour:

$$\int_C f(x(t) + iy(t)) dt = \iint_A f'(x', y') K'(x', y') dx' dy' \quad \text{Eq 66)}$$

Proof:

We can prove this with Greens theorem and converting the contour into the double integral and then transforming the double integral into the primed coordinates. It turns out that the conversion here to establish the relation between the contour and the double integral is sufficient to prove this theorem essentially by proving Greens theorem but Greens theorem has been proven and to avoid reinventing the wheel it really just needs to be established that the Greens theorem can be parameterized in the same it was used to convert the derivative in **Eq 59)**. The statement of Greens Theorem is:

$$\oint_C f(t) dt = \iint_D \left(\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) \right) dx dy \quad \text{Eq 67)}$$

The definition of the Complex contour after parameterization becomes:

$$\oint_C f(s) ds = \oint_C (U + iV)(dx + idy) = \oint_C (U dx - V dy) + i \oint_C (V dx + U dy) \quad \text{Eq 68)}$$

From which Greens Theorem can be used on both of the integrals on the RHS which show as well that the operation which is defined as the *kth* contour *i*:

$$\oint_c (Udx - Vdy) + i \oint_c (Vdx + Udy) = - \iint_D \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) dx dy + i \iint_D \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) dx dy \quad \text{Eq 69)}$$

The double integration over an area in the primed frame gives a volume. This contour here is not necessarily defined over a loop such as the Cauchy contours where the use in mind here to build such a relationship is motivated by performing arbitrary contours for arbitrary curves in the complex plane and converting this contour for Complex integration into the familiar form of multivariable FTOC to be extended to the complex domain. If the Taylor Expansion by **Eq 60**) of a function exists then the function must be analytic relative to *t*. The definition of the Cauchy Integral is:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_c \frac{f(t)}{t-z} dt \quad \text{Eq 70)}$$

Theorem:

If a Complex continuous function *f* has a Complex antiderivative *F* in \mathbb{C} and *C* is a curve in \mathbb{C} that begins at *t*₁ and ends at *t*₂, then

$$\int_c f(z) dz = F(t_2) - F(t_1) \quad \text{Eq 71)}$$

The antiderivative for *f* in \mathbb{C} is a function *F* that is holomorphic in \mathbb{C} and such that $\frac{d}{dz} F(z) = f(z)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{C}$, where that derivative is meant to be the Complex derivative. Also, *C* being smooth means that any of its parameterizations $z: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is continuously differentiable.

Proof:

Suppose there exists such a parameterization, and $z(a) = (t_1)$ and $z(b) = t_2$, then using the chain rule and the FTOC,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_c f(z) dz &= \int_{t=a}^{t=b} f(z(t)) * \frac{dz}{dt} dt \\ &= \int_{t=a}^{t=b} \frac{dF(z(t))}{dt} * \frac{dz}{dt} dt \\ &= \int_{t=a}^{t=b} \frac{d}{dt} F(z(t)) dt = F(z(b)) - F(z(a)) = F(t_2) - F(t_1) \end{aligned}$$

Define the product function: $H(z) = f(z)g(z)$, Then the Complex derivative is:

$$\frac{dH}{dz} = \lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{(f(z + \Delta z)g(z + \Delta z)) - (f(z)g(z))}{\Delta z} \quad \text{Eq 72)}$$

The clear representation of the derivative as a well-defined operator it can be seen that the replacement of *z* with *x* in **Eq 6**) for the single variable *x* will leave the formula unchanged. So all the derivative rules are essentially unchanged in the complex plane as well as the rules of integration. They are the same if differentiating and integrating with respect to the complex variable *z* but this requires the definition of the complex derivative as a 2 dimensional operator. Using

the definition of the complex derivative in **Eq 72**) the product rule for complex functions can be proven with the same method used to prove the real analytic case **Eq 6**). Stating the complex product rule:

$$\frac{d}{dz}(f(z)g(z)) = f(z)\left(\frac{dg(z)}{dz}\right) + g(z)\left(\frac{df(z)}{dz}\right) \quad \text{Eq 73)}$$

Where with the application of the Complex contour on **Eq 73**), the complex IBP formula can be stated as:

$$\int_a^z f(t)\left(\frac{dg(t)}{dt}\right) dt = f(t)g(t)|_a^z - \int_a^z g(t)\left(\frac{df(t)}{dt}\right) dt \quad \text{Eq 74)}$$

Where the constant a is assumed to be Complex valued for the Complex case. Essentially if a is a Complex constant and t is chosen parameterization such that the derivative relative to t is equivalent to the derivative relative to z as discussed above with the operator relationship.

Now, applying **Eq 74**) to **Eq 70**),

Complex Series Derivation: let $(w - z)^{-1} = f$, then by IBP acting on the Cauchy Integral we have:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C \frac{f(t)}{t-z} dt = \frac{\int_C f(t) dt}{(t-z)} \Big|_{t_1}^{t_2} - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{(-1)^1}{(t-z)^2} \left(\int_C f(t) dt \right) dt \quad \text{Eq 75)}$$

By defining the 2 order complex antiderivative as:

$$\int_C \left(\int_C f(t) dt \right) dt = \left(\int_C () dt \right)^2 f(t) = \frac{d^{-2}f(t)}{dt^{-2}} \quad \text{Eq 76)}$$

Expressing this as the derivative operator but with Leibnitz notation and negative k such as written above. Cauchy's repeated integration rule [17] can be used to express the n th integral of the function in a more simply manner.

Defining the k th operation of Complex IBP as \widehat{CIBP}_k and inserting the notation of **Eq 76**) into **Eq 75**) produces an Complex version of the real analytic equation in **Eq 25**):

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^{k=n} \widehat{CIBP}_k \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C \frac{f(t)}{t-z} dt \right) \\ = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left((t-z)^{-k} (-k)! \left(\frac{d^{-k}f}{dt^{-k}} \right) \right) \right) + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_a^z \left((t-z)^{-n} (-n)! \left(\frac{d^{-n+1}f}{dt^{-n+1}} \right) dt \right) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 77)}$$

The function for the Cauchy Integral in **Eq 70**) with the application of \widehat{CIBP}_k and the RHS of **Eq 77**) becomes:

$$f(z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left((t-z)^{-k} (-k)! \left(\frac{d^{-k}f}{dt^{-k}} \right) \right) \right) + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_a^z \left((t-z)^{-n} (-n)! \left(\frac{d^{-n+1}f}{dt^{-n+1}} \right) dt \right) \quad \text{Eq 78)}$$

Which, then using the Complex Taylor formula for $f(z)$ and **Eq 78**) a formula using both expressions can be constructed by linear combination [40]:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^2f &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\sum_{k=0}^{k=\infty} f_k(x) \right) + \left(\sum_{k=-\infty}^{k=0} f_k(x) \right) \right) \\ {}^2f &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\sum_{k=0}^{k=n} \left(\frac{(z-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k f(a)}{dz^k} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{k=n} (t+c)^{-k} (-k)! \left(\frac{d^{-k}f}{dt^{-k}} \right) \right) \right) + \frac{1}{2} ({}_1R_n + {}_2R_n) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 79)}$$

Now using method number 2 of integration by parts on the Cauchy formula, a third series representation of the function can be obtained and ultimately again express the function as a sum of all three series by:

$${}^3f = \frac{1}{3} \left(\left(\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(z-a)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{d^k f}{dt^k} \right) \right) \Big|_{\left(\frac{dx}{dt}=1, \frac{dy}{dt}=i \right)} \right) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=n} \left((t-z)^{-k} (-k)! \left(\frac{d^{-k} f}{dt^{-k}} \right) \right) \right) + (3^{rd} \text{ representation}) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^{p=3} \left(\sum_{w=1}^{w=n} \left(({}^p R_w) \right) \right) \right) \tag{Eq 80}$$

In this case, the first representation of the complex function f is its n th order Taylor series and for the LHS and the remainder for that function. The remainder for each series representation makes a remainder term which is a sum of all the remainder terms. Then a function can be defined if there exists k series representations generally as a sum of all of them. In the derivation of **Eq 78**), a third series representation for example could be derived by changing the order of IBP between the functions f and g in the **Eq 74**). The most general series would be a sum of all the series, divided by k , or a sum of each k th series divided by k . The k th representation of f is for n th degree can be obtained by summing over all orders w and representations p to the total number of representations k and the total order n . The exact form of that series is not of particular interest here, just the fact that it can be derived and there in general are k such representations that can be obtained in a similar manner. Generalizing **Eq 80**) leads to:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^{p=k} \left(\sum_{w=1}^{w=n} ({}^p f_w) \right) + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^{p=k} \left(\sum_{w=1}^{w=n} ({}^p R_w) \right) \tag{Eq 81}$$

In this notation, ${}^k f = f(z)$ is the k th representation of f since there are many different representations for each function and ${}^k R_n$ is the remainder term for the k th representation of n th order. By use of FTOC and an alternate selection of the constant $c = k(z)$ in the original proof of the Taylors theorem **Eq 29**) to achieve a term with the expression of the function instead of the usual Taylor polynomial form summing $(c_j(t-z)^j)$ this can be used to express the Complex function f instead as different sums and different types of remainder terms in the form: $c_j(t-z)^{-j}$, or in general, representing the Complex analytic function as a sum of other Complex analytic functions such as instead just considering all possible values for k in the sum. Taking $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty}$ (**Eq 81**)) produces:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{k=1}^{k=\infty} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{n=\infty} ({}^k f_n) \right) \tag{Eq 82}$$

This can be proven for Complex functions by defining the function as half of the regular Complex Taylor series **Eq 60**) plus half of **Eq 78**). This can be obtained from modifications of the function H in Taylors theorem as well as the generalized integral definition of the remainder function. The real analytic formulas for the Taylor theorem on H and H' can be used and then application the appropriate form to represent the function as a sum of other real analytic functions.

References

- [0] Widder D. V. "A Generalization of Taylor's Series," American Mathematical Society (AMS) 1926
- [1] Istvan A. Gal. "On the Fundamental Theorems of The Calculus," American Mathematical Society (AMS) 1956
- [2] Selby M. Allen, "Determinacy of Sufficiently Differentiable Maps," American Mathematical Society (AMS), 1988
- [3] Chang. Jun Seung, Choi Gil Jae, Skoug David, "Integration by Parts Formulas Involving Generalized Fourier-Feynman Transforms on Function Space," American Mathematical Society, 2003
- [4] Muirhead R. (1893) "E. Carpenter's Proof of Taylor's Theorem," Proceedings of the Edinburgh Mathematical Society (AMS)
- [5] Apostol, Tom, "Calculus, One-Variable Calculus, with an Introduction to Linear Algebra," John Wiley and Sons, 1967

- [6] Osler, J. Thomas, "An Integral Analogue of Taylor's Series and Its Use in Computing Fourier Transforms," AMS 1971
- [7] Appling D. L. William, "A Mapping Theorem for Logarithmic and Integration-By-Parts Operators," AMS 1975
- [8] Baeumer, Boris, Meerschaert M. Mark, Mortensen Jeff, "Space-Time Fractional Derivative Operators," AMS 2005
- [9] Upmeyer, "Jordan Algebras in Analysis, Operator Theory and Quantum Mechanics," AMS 1987
- [10] Constantine G, M., Savitis H, T., "A Multivariate Faà Di Bruno Formula with Applications," AMS 1996
- [11] Che Maolin, Wei Yimin, "Theory and Computation of Complex tensors and its Applications," Springer Singapore 2020
- [12] Morrey B. Charles, "Multiple Integrals In the Calculus of Variations," Springer 1966
- [13] Fritzsche Klaus, Grauert Hans, "From Holomorphic Functions to Complex Manifolds," Springer New York 2002
- [14] Ahlfors Lars, "Complex Analysis, An Introduction to the Theory of Analytic Functions of One Complex Variable," 2021
- [15] Shirazi Mohammad, "Faber and Grunsky Operators Corresponding to Bordered Riemann Surfaces," AMS 2020
- [16] Chan F Tony, Vassilevski S Panayot, "A Framework for Block ILU Factorizations using Block Sized Reduction," AMS 1992
- [17] Haddad, El Roudy, "Repeated Integration and Explicit Formula for the n th Integral of $x^m(\ln x)^m$," Arxiv